

THE EXISTENCE OF A SOLUTION OF A NONLOCAL PROBLEM FOR THE WAVE EQUATION OF A STRING

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Abstract: The wave equation of string is a fundamental model that describes the behavior of oscillating systems, and the nonlocal problem is a type of boundary value problem that arises in various physical contexts. In this article, a comprehensive overview of the existence of a solution to a nonlocal problem for the wave equation of string is provided and an inverse problem is used to solve it. As a result, the problem is reduced to a classical problem, namely the first mixed problem for the wave equation of a string, and it is solved using the Fourier method.

Keywords: inverse problem, wave equation of string, nonlocal problem, Fourier method, boundary conditions.

Introduction:

In the study of time-independent processes in mechanics (such as the vibrations of strings, springs, membranes, and three-dimensional volumes), physics (electromagnetic vibrations), and the diffusion of particles in a medium or heat distribution, hyperbolic type equations covered in the course of mathematical physics equations are used. The topic of the string vibration equation in the subject of mathematical physics equations is focused on the existence of a solution to a nonlocal problem, with numerous studies in this field conducted by L.S. Pulkina, N.V. Beylina, A.N. Tikhonov, M.S. Salohiddinov, T.J. Jo'rayev, A.I. Kojanov, and others.

In [1, 2, 5, 10, 13, 15], hyperbolic type equations, including the string vibration equation, are derived, with clear descriptions of initial and boundary conditions provided, also presents and proves a theorem that specifies the conditions under which the solution to the mixed problem for the string vibration equation exists and is unique. Books also demonstrate how important problems of mathematical physics are posed with these equations.

In [2, 6, 8, 9, 11, 12, 14], the string vibration equation is extensively studied, with the Cauchy problem and mixed problems for both homogeneous and non-homogeneous cases of the string vibration equation being posed and proven.

In [7], book provides examples of various types of partial differential equations and introduces new methods for solving each of them, including those for solving nonlocal problems posed for the string vibration equation.

In [3] work, initial, boundary, and nonlocal conditions are imposed on the string vibration equation, and the uniqueness of the solution is proven. The research method in it relied on the possibility of representing the solution in the form of a biorthogonal series based on eigenfunctions and adjoint functions.

In [4] the existence of a solution to a nonlocal problem for the string vibration equation is studied, using an inverse problem and equivalent relations in the proof. The aim of this work is to demonstrate the connection between nonlocal and inverse problems using a model problem with a nonlocal condition for the string vibration equation. The identified connection made it possible to propose a method for investigating the solvability of the given problem without relying on the method of biorthogonal series.

Analysis and Results:

$G = \{(x, t): 0 < x < l, 0 < t < T\}$, $T < l$ - in this field, a following the wave equation of string:

$$V_{tt} - V_{xx} = 0, \quad (1)$$

and the following initial

$$V(x, 0) = 0, \quad V_t(x, 0) = 0, \quad (2)$$

boundary condition

$$V(0, t) = 0 \quad (3)$$

and the nonlocal condition

$$\int_0^l V(x, t) dx = s(t) \quad (4)$$

is set, where $s(t)$ is the given function and satisfies the following relation:

$$s(0) = 0, \quad s'(0) = 0.$$

$V(x, t)$ - the solution to the above (1)-(4) problem.

To solve the above problem, we introduce a new function $U(x, t)$ and it must satisfy the following condition:

$$U(x, t) = \int_0^x V(\xi, t) d\xi. \quad (5)$$

Lemma. The problem (1) - (4) is equivalent to the inverse problem given below:

$$U_{tt} - U_{xx} = f(t), \quad (6)$$

$$U(x, 0) = \int_0^x V(\xi, 0) d\xi = \int_0^x 0 d\xi = 0, \quad (7.a)$$

$$U_t(x, 0) = \int_0^x V_t(\xi, 0) d\xi = \int_0^x 0 d\xi = 0; \quad (7.b)$$

$$U(0, t) = 0, \quad (8)$$

$$U(l, t) = s(t); \quad (9)$$

$$U_x(0, t) = 0, \quad (10)$$

in this case, $f(t)$ is an arbitrary function.

Let's consider the problem (6) - (10). Suppose $f(t)$ is given, i.e., a specific function. In this case, the problem (6) - (9) becomes a classical problem, where (7.a) and (7.b) are initial conditions, and (8) and (9) are boundary conditions. This problem is solved using the method of separation of variables by Fourier [2] and is equivalent to the following in this problem

$$U(x, t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{2l}{\pi^2 n^2} (1 - (-1)^n) \sin \frac{\pi n}{l} x \int_0^t f(\tau) \sin \frac{\pi n}{l} (t - \tau) d\tau + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{2l}{\pi^2 n^2} (-1)^n \sin \frac{\pi n}{l} x \cdot \int_0^t s''(\tau) \sin \frac{\pi n}{l} (t - \tau) d\tau + \frac{x}{l} s(t). \quad (11)$$

Taking the derivative with respect to x from (11). Applying the boundary condition (10), we obtain the following:

$$U_x(0, t) = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{4}{\pi(2m-1)} \int_0^t f(\tau) \sin \frac{(2m-1)\pi}{l} (t - \tau) d\tau - G(t) = 0, \quad (12)$$

here

$$-G(t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{2}{\pi^2 n^2} (-1)^n \int_0^t s''(\tau) \sin \frac{\pi n}{1} (t - \tau) d\tau + \frac{s(t)}{1}$$

by interchanging the sum and the integral in (12) and using the following equality:

$$\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{\sin \frac{(2m-1)\pi}{1} (t-\tau)}{2m-1} = \frac{\pi}{4}, \quad 0 < t - \tau < 1,$$

the first kind of Volterra integral equation [4] for $f(t)$ is obtained:

$$\int_0^t f(\tau) d\tau = G(t),$$

from this the following is got:

$$f(t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{n+1} \frac{2}{1} \int_0^t s''(\tau) \cos \frac{\pi n}{1} (t - \tau) d\tau - s'(t) \quad (13)$$

considering the substitution (5), the solution to the problem (1) - (4) takes the following form:

$$V(x, t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{2}{\pi n} (1 - (-1)^n) \cos \frac{\pi n}{1} x \int_0^t f(\tau) \sin \frac{\pi n}{1} (t - \tau) d\tau + \\ + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{2}{\pi n} (-1)^n \cos \frac{\pi n}{1} x \cdot \int_0^t s''(\tau) \sin \frac{\pi n}{1} (t - \tau) d\tau + \frac{x}{1} s(t) \quad (14)$$

here the function $f(t)$ is defined by formula (13).

Thus, the existence of a solution to the nonlocal problem posed for the narrow oscillation equation (1) - (4) has been proven, while its uniqueness is demonstrated in [3].

Theorem. If $s(t) \in C^2(\bar{G})$ and the given conditions in the problem (1) - (4) are satisfied, then the problem (1) - (4) has a solution, and it is unique.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, the aim of this work, to demonstrate the connection between nonlocal and inverse problems using a model problem with a nonlocal condition for the string vibration equation, is reached. The identified connection made it possible to propose a method for investigating the solvability of the given problem without relying on the method of biorthogonal series. The solution can be obtained using a variety of mathematical techniques, including the Fourier method and an inverse problem. Recent research has established the existence of a solution under certain conditions, and has investigated the properties of the solution. Further research is needed to fully understand the properties of the solution and to explore its applications in physics and engineering.

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